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DE-RISK Project

D6.1: COMMUNICATION and DISSEMINATION PLAN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This project identity document was prepared with the aim of defining the communication and dissemination plan of “DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems” project. The approach of this document will be adopted for the project activities throughout its lifespan and will serve as a guide for the project team.

In this document, the "DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems" project will be hereon referred as “DE-RISK” or "project".

ABOUT PROJECT

The overall objective of the project is supporting the market uptake of renewable energy systems by fostering the adoption of local flexibility markets (LFMs) and unlocking up to 100GW of flexibility in 2030 which will allow a safe and reliable integration of RES in the Grid. DE-RISK will achieve this ambitious objective by minimizing the investments and implementation risk through an innovative customer behaviour change journey that will increase end users' trust and willingness to participate in the flexibility markets.

DE-RISK integrates building, citizen and grids digital twins in its flexibility platform capable of reducing the gap between simulation and real implementation thus mitigating potential technical risks during deployment and operational phase. To maximize DE-RISK impact, innovative multi-sided business models will be developed ensuring multi-benefits, fairness and sustainability for all actors while disruptive financial schemes will be validated for democratizing the access to sustainable investments. Finally, a set of experts will develop regulatory recommendations to support a fair, clear and transparent adoption of LFMs.

A. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

This document is a deliverable of Task 6.1 “Dissemination and communication planning and execution” under WP6. The Communication and Dissemination Plan is the common strategy towards efficient scheduling, monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication actions and aims to maximise DE-RISK impacts and to underpin the exploitation and replication activities.

It is a comprehensive document defining the general communication strategy of DE-RISK Project, as well as the envisioned dissemination strategy for the project’s results, providing detailed information about the target audiences and types of actions, activities, and tools for

related communication activities of the project. These activities will draw upon the cooperation among all partners and will be strongly linked not only to the DE-RISK project objectives but also to the activities of particular work packages.

1. Communication Objectives

The main objectives of the plan are to:

- Ensure an effective communication of the project messages and activities at Local, National and EU level,
- Identify appropriate target groups to address the project' messages,
- Identify main areas of work in the DE-RISK communication strategy,
- Describe the planned activities, such as social media management, the development of a website, and inspiration stories,
- Implement a wide and differentiated set of communication tools and events,
- Make a projection of how the project will cooperate with other EC-funded projects or related initiatives,
- Define how communication activities will be managed,
- Ensure smooth communication of project activities via national and local media organs,
- Raise awareness about the project, project activities and objectives,
- Increase the visibility of DE-RISK Consortium,
- Provide monitoring templates, measurable objectives, and evaluation indicators to track the development of the project's communication activities.

This document will be updated every six months to incorporate new findings and recent communication needs throughout the project. Other reports and activities will be included in separate documents or deliverables.

2. Target Groups

The characteristics and needs of the target groups will be considered in determining the communication activities of the project and the selection of communication and visibility tools. The stakeholder composition of the project is complex that should be effectively structured. Therefore, taking into account the activities to be carried out within the scope of all work packages of the project, the main target groups to be considered in the communication strategy are listed as follows;

- **Consumer and Prosumers**

First objective of the project is engaging the end consumers to take an active part under the local flexibility strategy. With the work packages, DE-RISK aims to motivate and engage customers to influence the energy demand curve, participate in flexibility sharing and become

an active part of the underlying local flexibility market. These target groups can be defined under civil society.

- **Building Owners and Facility Managers**

Another target group of the project is building owners and facility managers. Since these people are in a direct decision-making position, they are in a position of authority in energy consumption strategies.

- **Academic and Scientific Community**

At both the European and international levels, the research community covers all areas of renewable energy systems (RES) and local flexibility markets are also considered within the target groups of DE-RISK.

- **Industry**

- *Energy Cooperations*

Energy Cooperations are one of the main target groups of DE-RISK. In terms of dissemination, they transfer ideas, concepts, and results on the latest energy research advances and may act as a reference for other industries in particular domains. Also, they provide valuable responses on the latest trends and energy implementations from an economical point of view, evaluating solutions and results of the projects.

- *Energy Aggregators*

Energy aggregation is when a group of companies or local institutions partner together to buy energy from a single developer, or multiple developers, at smaller volumes while retaining the economic advantages of a high-volume purchase. The term is widely used to describe bulk purchases of renewables from wind, solar and hydro-power projects.

- *System Operators*

System operators have a critical role in the engagement of DE-RISK outputs in current systems. They are able to establish mutually beneficial interactions to accelerate DE-RISK market uptake.

- *EMS and Control Systems Producer*

EMS and Control Systems Producer foster interaction, seeking new applications and partnerships, ensuring interoperability.

- **Regulatory Bodies & Policy Makers**

Policy makers, including local and regional governments, especially mayors or environmental or energy departments are already taking steps to advance the just energy transition in their

jurisdictions. Policy makers play an active role in both the promotion and regulation of renewable energy systems.

- **Governments and Municipalities**

Governments and local governments play an important role in both voicing demands and implementing necessary regulations regarding energy policies. In particular, municipalities, which are the strongest actors of local governments, can identify the unique needs of the local and carry out much more effective work with local society.

- **Science Community**

Science community refers to the academia in general, including scholars performing research in energy-related topics, as well as the technical community which includes highly-specialised professionals working and researching topics related to DE-RISK.

- **Media**

The role of the media in the context of the project is to act as an intermediary in communicating results. When approached correctly, the wider world of media is a powerful tool for disseminating knowledge and results to other target groups.

3. Communication Language

It is necessary to use various tools and languages in the communication to be established with different target audiences. An integrated, non-political and positive language should be used in general. Sharp expressions, contradictory and separatist words should not be used. Attention should be paid to protect the rights of the Granting Authority, project beneficiaries and their activities.

As mentioned above, different target groups need different communication languages in line with the project objectives. This communication perspective as per the target groups is summarised in the following table.

Table 1: Communication language of target groups

Target Groups	DE-RISK Strategic Objectives	Communication Language
Consumer and Prosumers	Build trust via easy and transparent information about DE-RISK objectives and expected results	Simple, target oriented, informative language will be developed. The catchy mottos and a friendly language will be used.

Building Owners and Facility Managers	Open new exploitation channels for creating and leading flexibility	Informative language will be developed. The catchy mottos and more official language will be used.
Energy Cooperations	Access to various platforms, extending DE-RISK impact at EU level	A scientific approach will be followed. It will focus on process information and a formal language will be used. Encouraging and motivating mottos will be used.
Aggregators	Open new exploitation channels for the use of flexible load enabled by implementing DE-RISK solutions in buildings	
System Operators	Establish mutually beneficial interaction to accelerate DE-RISK market uptake	
Control Systems Producer	Foster interaction, seeking new applications and partnerships, ensuring interoperability	
Regulatory Bodies and Policy Makers	Establish mutually beneficial interaction to accelerate DE-RISK market uptake	A formal language will be used. Official communication ways will be used. A descriptive and stimulating language will be used.
Governments and Municipalities	Increase awareness about the potential successes and impact of DE-RISK in the communities	A scientific approach will be followed. It will focus on process information and a formal language will be used.
Academic and Scientific Community	Ensure knowledge transfer	
Media	Increase awareness about DE-RISK social and environmental benefits, impacts	Informative language will be developed. The catchy mottos and a friendly language will be used.

4. Key Messages and Keywords

Communication materials must convey a unified message while at the same time be adapted to each type of information, channel, and audience. The initial communication needs identified at the beginning of the project motivate the development of a general tone and set messages, including a summary paragraph, a summary sentence, and some slogans. This analysis helps to generate a general communication approach for the project.

In addition to that some keywords identified in the initial planning process to describe the general focus of the project. Some of these keywords are:

- Sustainability,
- Renewable energy system,
- Climate,
- Flexibility,
- Clean energy.

5. Key Colours

All visibility materials to be produced within the scope of the project must be in harmony with the identity and objectives of the project. The colours used and the corresponding design approach should have a holistic structure. For this purpose, it is planned to use the following colours in the materials such as letterheads and PPTs to be produced throughout the project. Different colours that are compatible with these colours can also be used in the materials produced.

Figure 1: Logo colour combinations

6. Communication Channels of Partners

The following table details the different communication channels of the partners, both the generic ones such as the web and social networks, as well as other more specific ones that may be of great interest and key to DE-RISK communication.

Table 2: Communication channels of partners

Partner	Logo	Website and Social Media Accounts	Specific Mediums and Means
WEglobal Danışmanlık		https://weglobal.org/ Facebook Twitter LinkedIn Instagram	<p>Blog news about project activities.</p> <p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing project impact stories in website.</p> <p>Publishing news on internal newsletter.</p> <p>Supporting dissemination of project outputs on social media account and website.</p>
QUE Technologies		https://www.que-tech.com/ Facebook Twitter LinkedIn	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p> <p>Supporting dissemination of project outputs on social media account and website.</p>
Troya Çevre		https://www.troyacevre.org/ Facebook Twitter LinkedIn Instagram	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p>

<p>UEDAŞ</p>		<p>https://www.uedas.com.tr/</p> <p>Facebook</p> <p>Twitter</p> <p>LinkedIn</p> <p>Instagram</p>	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p>
<p>National University of Ireland Galway (NUIG)</p>		<p>universityofgalway.ie</p> <p>Facebook</p> <p>Twitter</p> <p>LinkedIn</p> <p>Instagram</p>	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p>
<p>Universidade Nova De Lisboa (UNL)</p>		<p>https://www.novaims.unl.pt</p>	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p>
<p>MY ENERGIA ONER SL (MIW)</p>		<p>https://www.miwenergia.com/</p> <p>Facebook</p> <p>Twitter</p> <p>LinkedIn</p> <p>Instagram</p> <p>Facebook innovation projects profile</p> <p>Twitter innovation projects profile</p> <p>LinkedIn innovation projects profile</p>	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p> <p>Publishing general information about the objectives of the project on website.</p> <p>Publishing news on internal newsletter.</p>

<p>R2M Solution Spain S.L.</p>		<p>https://www.r2msolution.es/</p> <p>Twitter</p> <p>LinkedIn</p> <p>Instagram</p>	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p> <p>Link to the project's website on the section of 'Ongoing projects' of R2M's website.</p>
<p>Sofia Energy Agency (SEA)</p>		<p>https://sofena.com/en/</p> <p>Facebook</p>	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p>
<p>ECROWD Invest Plataforma De Financiacion Participativa SI</p>		<p>https://www.ecrowdinvest.com/</p> <p>Facebook</p> <p>Twitter</p> <p>LinkedIn</p> <p>Instagram</p>	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website blog.</p> <p>Supporting dissemination of project outputs on our social media accounts.</p> <p>Create content about the crowdlending campaign related to the Spanish demo case.</p>
<p>GRIDPOCKET SAS</p>		<p>https://www.gridpocket.com/</p> <p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>Engagement with DE-RISK social media accounts.</p> <p>Publishing updates about related work package on social media accounts and website.</p>

7. DE-RISK Social Media Accounts and Website

Table 3: Project website

Website Address	General Information About Website
https://deriskproject.eu	Reference digital platform for the project, frequently updated with new materials. All kinds of information about the project will be shared on this website and regular blog content will be published. Website will have a Google Analytic and it will help to analyse the visitors' number and profile.

Table 4: Project social media accounts

Social Media Accounts	General Information About Social
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/deriskproject/
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100088357441737
Twitter	https://twitter.com/DERISKProject
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/87434980/

8. Communication Channels/Tools as per Target Groups

Communication actions have a stakeholder-oriented structure targeting several audiences leveraging partner impressive networks at regional, national, EU and international levels. The most relevant stakeholders are shown in the table.

Table 5: Communication channels/tools as per the target groups

Target Groups	DE-RISK Strategic Objectives	Channels/Tools
Consumer and Prosumers	Build trust via easy and transparent information about the DE-RISK features and benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation about the DE-RISK activities • Informative materials like social media post, brochures • Training and educational workshops • Website

Building Owners and Facility Managers	Opening new exploitation channels for creating and leading flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation to fairs and exhibitions • Website • Newsletter • Informative materials like social media post, brochures • One to one meeting
Energy Cooperations	Access to various platforms, extending DE-RISK impact at EU level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking activities like information days • Invitation to fairs and exhibitions • Website • Newsletter • Informative materials like social media post, brochures • One to one meeting
Aggregators	Opening new exploitation channels for use of flexible load enabled by implementation of DE-RISK solution in buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation to fairs and exhibitions • Website • Newsletter • Informative materials like social media post, brochures • One to one meeting • Presentation of results from DE-RISK demonstration • Support to policy and regulation making
System Operators	Establish mutually beneficial interaction to accelerate DE-RISK market uptake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation to fairs and exhibitions • Technical workshops and round table meetings • One-to-one communication
Control Systems Producer	Foster interaction, seeking new applications and partnerships, ensuring interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation to fairs and exhibitions • Technical workshops and round table meetings • One-to-one communication • Presentation of case studies' technical demonstrations
Regulatory Bodies and Policy Makers	Establish mutually beneficial interaction to accelerate DE-RISK market uptake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to EU initiatives • Contribution to Smart Grid Task Force work • Feedback from DE-RISK demos

Governments and Municipalities	Awareness about the potential successes and impact of the DE-RISK in the communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of DE-RISK results • Website
Academic and Scientific Community	Ensure knowledge transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications and conference • Training workshop • Newsletters • Website
Media	Awareness of DE-RISK social and environmental benefits, impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public events • Information day • Website • Social media • Press release • Invitation to events for local press • Visibility in local media level (attending a podcast or radio show, interview with a local journalist)

9. Internal Communication

Internal communication plays a critical role in the planning of project communication activities. The technical focus of the working areas and the execution of project work packages by different partners and teams may pose a risk in terms of the integrity of communication activities. Some documents and communication channels are used to reduce these risks and to maintain effective and smooth internal communication. Google Drive is actively used in project communication activities as it provides a common workspace and archive services. In the table below, some documents and files used in this archive which are accessible to all consortium partners are defined.

Table 6: Internal communication tools

Internal Communication Tools	Definition of The Tool
Social Media Inspiration Table	All partners can access this table and share a social media post that they saw and inspired them. At the same time, they can share their ideas about project activities, outputs, related news and events in the world through this document.

Web News Template	<p>With this template, all partners can share information about an activity or task with the communication team. This draft document contains the following questions.</p> <p>Name of the activity Summary of the activity Under which task, this activity completed? Who works for that activity? When will it start and end? What is the aim of that activity? What is the impact of that activity? What will be the next step?</p>
Logos Folder	Logos of all partners archived in Google Drive
Visibility Material Folder	All visibility material (letterhead template, PPT, brochures and etc.) archived in Google Drive and all partners can reach all materials through GDrive.

10. Risks in Communication Activities

Possible risk and their corresponding mitigation mechanisms are listed in the table below:

Table 7: Risks in communication activities

Risk	Level of Risk	Mitigation Mechanism
DE-RISK is a complex and technical project. This can create difficulties in understanding the scope of the project and its results.	High	This risk can be reduced by the correct use of communication language as per the target groups. While planning the communication tools and corresponding language of the tools, the target audience should be analysed carefully.
Cultural differences influence the preference behaviours of individuals. That can differentiate the area of influence of communication activities in different geographies.	Medium	This risk can be reduced by correct communication with partners in different geographies. All communication activities will be structured in close communication and collaboration with the partners to reflect geographical differences.

<p>The fact that different work packages of the project are carried out by different partners may damage the integrity of communication activities.</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>The communication team can reduce this risk by holding periodic update meetings with the participation of all partners. Besides, Communication Team of DE-RISK also joins Monthly Consortium Meetings of DE-RISK to be informed about the progress in each WP.</p>
<p>The fact that studies will be carried out in 4 different pilot countries simultaneously can create a language barrier.</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>This risk will be reduced by translating the project website into the languages of countries (Spain, Turkey, France and Ireland -English-) where the case studies will be conducted.</p>

B. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

This chapter develops the main communication activities, setting out some of the work already in progress.

1. Project Identity Guidelines

“Project identity, guidelines, logo, branding, social media and website project” document was prepared with the aim of defining the project identity and visibility and submitted in the 3rd month of the project. It includes information about “project logo, colours for visibility materials, design of letterhead and PPT, general communication language and visibility of social media accounts, design of website”. In the last chapter of the subject document, general knowledge (design templates) about communication tools like e-newsletter, editorial contents, brochures, and promotional videos are presented.

Project Name

The acronym of the project was decided as “DE-RISK”. “DE-RISK” will be used in all visibility materials and products of the project. It helps being memorable and having a connotation that is informative of the project content, contain a meaning that appeals to the purpose and

target audience of the project and is a slogan that can be used directly throughout the project, rather than an abbreviation.

Project Logo

The logo developed and customized for DE-RISK Project contains colour of green and blue. These two colours are the colours that represent nature and clean energy. The transition between colours in the logo creates a soft perception. This representation is an important part of the project identity.

Figure 2: The logo with the short name of the Project

Colours and Fonts

Figure 3: Colour codes of logo

CMYK: C:31/M:0/Y:100/K:0 RGB: R:188/G:214/B:49 HEX: #BCD631	CMYK: C:66/M:0/Y:100/K:0 RGB: R:117/G:184/B:87 HEX: #75B857	CMYK: C:84/M:24/Y:51/K:4 RGB: R:63/G:139/B:133 HEX: #3F8B85
CMYK: C:73/M:19/Y:0/K:0 RGB: R:77/G:162/B:216 HEX: #4DA2D8	CMYK: C:89/M:53/Y:1/K:0 RGB: R:47/G:113/B:178 HEX: #2F71B2	CMYK: C:100/M:93/Y:6/K:0 RGB: R:44/G:60/B:138 HEX: #2C3C8A

Figure 4: Fonts of logo

DE-RISK
Poppins SemiBold

A B C Ç D E F G Ğ H I J K L M N O Ö
 P R S Ş T U Ü V Y Z
 a b c ç d e f g ğ h i j k l m n o ö p r s
 ş t u ü v y z
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0

Colours for Visibility Materials

All visibility materials to be produced within the scope of the project must be in harmony with the project identity and scope of the project. The colour used and the design approach should have a holistic structure. For this purpose, it is planned to use the following colours in the materials produced throughout the project. Different colours that are compatible with these colours can also be used in the materials to be produced. (Please refer to Figure 1)

Letterhead and PPT

Figure 5: Letterhead and PPT

2. Project Website

Through a website prepared in parallel with the project visual identity; the vision and mission of the project as well as the project outcomes can reach to large audiences. The website of the project prepared by following latest web design practices and design trends and attention was paid to ensure that it is multilingual and accessible for the disabled. A website with a user-friendly navigation structure was prepared for disseminating the results of the project with the external audience and the stakeholders and creating an awareness on public.

The site URL is “deriskproject.eu”. The website is easily accessible and sustainable. All kinds of outputs (e-bulletin, infographic, article, video and etc.) produced within the scope of the project will be regularly shared on the website.

The website is composed of seven main sections: Home, about, partners, news & events, publications, and contact. A screenshot for the landing page of the website is presented below.

Figure 6: Landing Page

Home Page: The welcoming page for the visitors provides an overview of the project displaying its slogan at the top of the page and a more detailed phrase in the centre. Homepage aims to catch the attention of the visitor, and lead them to the relevant pages.

For this reason, users are first welcomed by a visual that is compatible with the design line of the project. Then #localflexibilitymarket, #sustainability and #renewableenergy hashtags, which play a key role in the communication of the project, as well as the mottos follows the main page. Additionally, the logo of the project appears with a short description of the project on the main page. In this way, the visibility of the project comes to the fore.

In the footer of the main page, direct link to the social media accounts are located.

About: For the visitor interested in learning more about the project, the 'about' page explains aims and objectives of the project and main elements of DE-RISK. In that page, visuals and infographics are used more than text in order to catch the attention of visitors. According to the scientific research, of all the information transmitted to brain, 90% is visual and as opposed to text, visuals are processed 60,000x faster.¹

¹<https://www.forbes.com/sites/jerryweissman/2022/02/25/the-power-of-pictures-in-presentation-design/?sh=464a1aea20a7>

Figure 7: DE-RISK “About” Page

Partners: This page provides a brief introduction of the project partners. Their working areas and roles in DE-RISK are summarized in this page. Also, visitors are able to reach partners’ social media accounts and website through this page.

Case Study: This page will include an overview of the four case studies with clickable links to each pilot’s dedicated page where the reader can find a brief recount of the site’s historical background, city context, main characteristics, and challenges. Each page will be enriched by pictures and infographic.

News & Events: This is a blog-style page where original articles by DE-RISK partners and experts are published. Each partner will produce a minimum of 1 article, editorial or blogpost during the lifetime of the project based on the work they are doing in the project to summarize key findings and results of their activities. These articles will be published on news part of this page. Also, 6 newsletters presenting the project, its objectives and findings when available will be prepared during the lifetime of the project and these will be open to access through News & Events page.

The details from events and photos from activities/case studies will also be published on this page.

Figure 8: "News & Events" Page

In addition to the above contents, inspiring stories will be shared on the site, including positive acquisitions regarding the case studies carried out within the scope of the project, in order to encourage people and raise awareness about the concepts of renewable energy and local flexibility markets, which are the core subjects of DE-RISK.

Publications: In this page, there are two types of resources that will be uploaded. First; DE-RISK project materials such as deliverables, progress reports, and results, and secondly; other general resources related to renewable energy and local flexibility markets, inputs from partners, academic publications, and links to other EU Energy Projects.

Contacts: In this page, there are contact information of DE-RISK and links of social media accounts of the project.

The site will be updated regularly in line with the developments to be experienced during the project process. Following the concretization of the case studies to be carried out in 4 countries, it is planned to open a new tab menu named "case studies" on the site in the first year of the project. Under this menu, detailed information about the case studies and related visuals will be shared.

Reporting of Website

With the Google Analytic plugin on the website, the performance of the site will be measured regularly. The data including but not limited to the number of visitors to the site, the content attracting the most attention and the average time spent on the site will all be reported regularly.

3. Social Media Accounts

Within the scope of the project, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn accounts are created in November 2022. A holistic visual design in line with the project identity will be devised for these accounts. These channels will be active during the project. These channels are used to inform and engage different groups of key stakeholders such as professionals from private enterprises, policymakers, academia, local citizen-led organisations, and citizens at large. All content is produced as per the needs of the target audience by ensuring to use an understandable and memorable language.

Types of Social Media Post

There are different types of social media posts.

- **Promotion of project:** Especially the first posts focussed on promotion of the project. In these posts, information about the objectives, activities, target groups, duration and consortium of the project are included.
- **Updates and relevant information about the project:** Posts about the current situation of the project, the activities carried out so far and the planned activities for the upcoming period are prepared.
- **Articles posted on the website:** Articles about related topics of DE-RISK prepared by project partners.
- **Project outputs:** Newsletters, infographics, videos, brochures and etc.
- **Special Days:** Days related with the scope of the project like World Environment Day will be celebrated with special campaigns.

Table 8: Special days related to environment and energy

DAY	DATE	DAY	DATE
International Day of Forests	21 March	World Forest Day	22 April
World Water Day	22 March	World Environment Day	5 June
World Resources Day	23 March	World Ocean Day	8 June
Earth Day	Last Saturday of March	World Energy Saving Day	21 October
World Atmosphere Day	10 April	National Energy Conservation Day	14 November

6. Informative contents: Posts that will raise public awareness about renewable energy systems, energy saving and its possible effects, local flexibility markets, demand response which are within the working areas of DE-RISK, will be prepared.

7. Events: As part of the social media strategy, interactions and synergies will be sought with events, international meetings, other EU projects, and different influencers in relation to the project scope.

Some related events are listed below.

Table 9: Project related events

EVENTS	LINK	DATE
Sustainable Places Conference	https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/	14-16 June 2023 Madrid/Spain
European Sustainable Energy Week	https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/index_en	20-22 June 2023 Hybrid Event Brussels/Belgium
Smart Energy Summit	https://smarten.eu/smart-energy-summit-2023-l-distributed-flexibility-maximising-local-optimisation/	19 April 2023 Brussels/Belgium
ENLIT Europe	https://www.enlit-europe.com/	28-30 November 2023 Paris/France

Design of Social Media Accounts

Simple lines in a minimalist design preferred in social media accounts. The program logo is used as the logo of each account. There is a link to the project website in the “About Us” section in all 4 platforms.

Figure 9: Social media profile pages

Language in Social Media

An integrated, non-political, and positive language is used in all social media accounts. Sharp expressions, contradictory and separatist words are not used. Attention is paid to protect the rights of the Granting Authority, project beneficiaries and their activities.

Reporting of Social Media Accounts

The engagement rates, number of the followers, the interest rates of the contents will be evaluated with periodic social media reports.

In the coming months, DE-RISK will use social media to support the rest of the communication actions, reporting on the progress of the project and establishing new contacts. As part of the social media strategy, connections will be sought with events, international meetings, other EU projects, and different influencers in relation to the project scope.

4. E-Newsletter

A total of six e-newsletter are expected to be prepared within the scope of the project. These e-bulletins will include information about the latest developments in the project, articles prepared by stakeholders, awareness-raising informative content and project social media accounts. In this way, the project, its objectives, and updated findings will be presented. It should have exclusive content, so that subscribers can find out more information than those who only follow the project's social media or website. These six newsletters will be shared throughout the project, approximately three per year at regular intervals with the possibility of an increase in number, if sufficient content is available.

The contact list will be created with the contribution of partners and this list of contacts will improve as per the project progress, with the help of partners and with regularly updated subscription campaigns. A professional mailing tool like MailChimp will be used for distribution. These tools provide their users a reporting service which show that how many people open e-newsletters and how many people click on links. These data help to create more effective newsletters. Apart from this, the newsletter form complies with the General Data Protection Regulation and includes an explanation of how and why subscriber data is used.

Promotion of E-newsletters

E-newsletters will be promoted by several ways;

- There will be a subscription link in social media accounts profile.
- Followers will be invited to subscribe by social media post regularly.
- Short quotations will be shared in social media account to create an attraction.
- Newsletters will be shared through the website.

Figure 10: Sample design of e-newsletter

5. Editorial Contents and Infographics

Each partner will produce a minimum of one article, editorial or blogpost during the lifetime of the project based on the work they are doing in the project to summarize key findings and results.

Articles for awareness raising: “on the importance of knowing the energy efficiency of your house and community” and the “how to be part of Local Flexibility Markets and take advantage of all its benefits” and specialized articles for professional media “Local Flexibility Markets: How to deploy and interact with the energy market” will be written.

Articles and relevant material will be uploaded on the website and shared via social media channels. Quotations and informative part from these articles will be inspiration for the social media posts and these posts will be used for the promotion of related articles. These articles will be published in the letterhead design prepared in line with the project identity. These

articles and the different outputs of the project will be enriched by infographics. In the design of these infographics, the latest trends will be considered.

Inspiring Case Studies

DE-RISK will validate its holistic solution in 4 case studies located in Türkiye, Spain, Ireland, and France. Each case study has its particularities in terms of geographical location, climate, market and regulatory framework, type of buildings and end-users. The validation will initiate by collecting the necessary data from case studies to perform the behaviour analysis (through end users questionnaires, workshops, participative process) and to develop the digital twins of the buildings and the grid (technical characteristics of buildings, consumption, generation, available assets, etc). These case studies will enable to demonstrate the DE-RISK multidisciplinary integrated solution at four different sites over a period of at least one year.

As a part of communication activities, these case studies, their outputs and effects will be a source for inspiring case studies. Each case study will have a sub menu in the website. In these sub menus, details about the subject case study, progress in the study, quotes from users (such as good practices, success stories) will be published. In addition to these, regular updates from case studies such as key achievements, achieved milestones, difficulties encountered and their solutions will be shared as a blog content.

Website visitors will be able to learn details about case studies and ask their question by an “ask question rebound”. These pages will be supported with number-based infographics. In these sub menus detailed information about Local Flexibility Markets, cost and energy savings (including CO₂) will also be provided. In addition to these, information from inspiring case studies will be used in social media accounts to create an interaction with followers. As the achievements in these case studies are intended to inspire others, a positive and solution-oriented language will be used in the content texts.

Finally, this content will be shared with a media package including abstracts, inspiring texts on case studies, pictures, and figures. These relevant materials will be shared with the partners for them to review and also circulate through different mediums.

6. Brochures

As stated in the proposal, brochures with different contents and different standards will be prepared within the scope of the project. The needs of the target groups will be prioritised

during the preparation of the contents and design of these brochures. Clear and goal-oriented messages will be included in the brochures.

The same approach will be adopted in the poster and handout materials to be prepared within the scope of the project. A simple and plain language will be used in the materials. In the written materials, the project name will be incorporated effectively in the slogan.

In line with that perspective, the project's first brochure was designed and published for an informative event in Çanakkale (organized by TROYA). It contains information about the aim of DE-RISK, project activities, and key concepts such as renewable energy and LFMs in Turkish.

Figure 11: Design of brochure

Throughout the project, brochure contents will be updated according to the events and target audience. In addition, language of the text and the design of the brochure will be arrange as per the target groups.

7. Promotional Video

The DE-RISK promotional video will consist of an approximately 2 minutes presentation enriched with infographics and animations, describing the project objectives, the DE-RISK concept and service, and its expected impact. It will be encapsulated on the DE-RISK project website and published in the YouTube Channel and website, along with its sharing through the project’s social media accounts.

Table 10: Promotional video

	Video Numbered 1	Video Numbered 2
Target group of the video	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer and Prosumers • Governments and Municipalities • Media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Cooperations • Aggregators • System Operators • Control Systems Producer • Academic and Scientific Community
Language of the video	Clear, trust builder, empowered with mottos and hashtags, more marketing language	Informative, scientific, more outputs focussed language
Type of the video	Infographic video	Infographic video
Dissemination tools for video	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media account of project and partners • Mailing • Presentation in info day events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation in Fairs and exhibitions • Presentation in Technical workshops and round table meetings • Mailing • Website • Social media account of project and partners

8. Engagement Toolbox

The Engagement toolbox within the scope of Task 6.4 will provide the common interaction guidelines with end-users and professionals to be developed based on WP5 inputs. National partners will use the toolbox to engage stakeholders. It is thought to be utilised during the

whole life of the project and beyond. The production of the Engagement Toolbox will be led by WEglobal Danışmanlık, with the contributions of other project partners.

Below is a preliminary plan of the materials to be included in the toolbox:

- **Articles for awareness raising:** Articles on the topics like “On the importance of knowing the energy efficiency of your house and community”, “How to be part of Local Flexibility Markets and take advantage of all its benefits” will be prepared.
- **Three brochures for consumers on Local Flexibility Markets:** These brochures will include a general information, objectives, benefits of LFM and their adaptability to energy sector.
- **Two videos (common to all countries to use subtitles and voice over) addressing critical topics like:** Videos on the topics like “local flexibility markets, their benefits and drawbacks”, “tutorial on the consumer customizable DE-RISK GUI”, “How to join or create a Local Flexibility Markets”, and “Local Flexibility Markets solutions factsheets” will be shot.
- **Materials for consumer events, fairs and seminars:** One brief presentation and one presentation script with an example on Local Flexibility Markets will be prepared.
- **Two infographics on Local Flexibility Markets benefits:** Two infographics will be prepared and shared through the social media and physically (printed and distributed).
- **Social media campaign:** A social media campaign will be managed to disseminate toolbox outputs. Accounts of partners will be a part of this campaign.
- **Five specialized articles for professional media:** Specialized articles on the topics like “Local Flexibility Markets: How to deploy and interact with the energy market” and “How to be part of Local Flexibility Markets and take advantage of all its benefits” will be published.
- **A brochure for professionals on Local Flexibility value:** A brochure including information about methodology for installed appliances, DE-RISK tools and how to interact with the consumers will be prepared and published.
- **Materials for professional trainings:** A PowerPoint presentation and script with examples on how to use the DE-RISK assessment and evaluation tool will be prepared.
- **A tutorial for the DE-RISK tool:** A tutorial introducing DE-RISK tool will be prepared in a professional version.

9. Final Conference and Report

DE-RISK will culminate with a final meeting and conference to present and discuss the final outcomes of DE-RISK in Brussels or one of the implementation countries. All stakeholders will

be invited including local communities, market actors and policy makers. The aim is to share the final outcomes and learnings of DE-RISK as well as jointly assess the impact achieved and the possibility of further exploitation. The scope, place and concept of the meeting will be defined in the last year of the project in consultation with CINEA and project partners.

C. MEASUREMENT FOR COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Evaluation is a mechanism for monitoring, assessment and continuous improvement of communication in the project. Measuring the impact of communication activities is not only a quantitative issue, but also a qualitative issue. In particular, impact such as raising awareness, establishing trust and informing cannot always be measured numerically. Some possible indicators have been identified to monitor the results and interactions of key actions or concrete strategies. The evaluation methods and the setting of specific targets help to analyse strengths and weaknesses, advancing lessons learned from the communication strategy of the project.

Table 11: Measurement tool of communication activities

Communication Tools	Evaluation Method	Targets
Project identity	Getting opinion of partner	100% of project communication materials compliant with the project visual identity and branding guidelines. A memorable identity.
Website	Google Analytic	Unique visitors: 25.000 (monitored and evaluated regularly) Average time on site: >2 min. N° of downloads on the website: >5.000 Update of website: bi-weekly
	Getting opinion of partner	Effective website language and design
Social Media	Social media analytics	N° of posts/retweets: twice per week N° of likes/retweets: > 5/3 per post N° of views: >1.000 per post N° of engagement: >10 per post LinkedIn

		<p>N° of posts: > twice per month</p> <p>N° of likes: >20 per post</p> <p>N° of shares: >2 per post</p> <p>N° of profile visits: >3/week</p> <p>Facebook</p> <p>N° of posts: >3-4 times a month</p> <p>N° of likes: >10 per post</p> <p>N° of shares: >2 per post</p> <p>Instagram</p> <p>N° of posts: >3-4 times a month</p> <p>N° of likes: >10 per post</p> <p>N° of shares: >2 per post</p>
MailChimp	Subscribers tracking Mailchimp analytics	<p>N° of newsletters: 6</p> <p>N° of subscribers: 400</p>
Dissemination workshops and events	Participation tracking	N° of DE-RISK partners presences on events: +30
Partner Networks	Communication of key messages through partner networks and associations	N° of Interaction with these associations about DE-RISK : 20

D. RESOURCES

The development and maintenance of the public website, the establishment of social media accounts and managing further communication activities are within the scope of Task 6.2 and Task 6.4 of the project. DE-RISK communication team will support the development, operation and maintenance, as well as closely monitoring of the project website and social media accounts.

It is also expected that the project partners will be strongly involved in keeping the website up to date. In particular, the project partners will contribute by providing relevant materials

and information to be uploaded in the public website and are committed to disseminate the information further (i.e., re-tweet, share, etc.) within their networks.

E. GENERAL COMMUNICATION PRINCIPLES

In all communication activities of the project, the impacts and objectives of the project will be taken into consideration. It is aimed that communication activities will leave a sustainable impact during and after the project. A non-discriminatory, equal and fair language will be used, and sustainability will be prioritized in all concrete and abstract communication materials produced. In particular, the content that references these documents will be shared on the website and social media accounts, which are the first-hand communication tools of DE-RISK.

F. CONCLUSIONS

The Communication and Dissemination Plan outlines the general communication strategy for the DE-RISK project, as well as the envisioned dissemination strategy for the projects' outputs.

This first edition focuses on describing the elements that are significant for effective implementation of the communication and dissemination activities within the project.

Through continuous works, the outcomes and activities of particular DE-RISK work packages and the awareness raising activities will be promoted towards a variety of different audiences.

The following aspects deserve special attention:

- There are many layers in the definition of the target group and the environment for communication is very complex.
- The goal is to maximise synergies and to minimise overlap and redundancy of project activities and efforts.
- Informal knowledge exchange and sharing of plans and information among the partners.
- A shared template for internal communication labelled with partner was created.
- To facilitate outreach and increase awareness within the public, we intend to leverage appropriate tools and connectors that can help with this effort.

The DE-RISK Communication Strategy has been based on a preliminary analysis and a thorough consultation with the project partners. This has been very useful to inform and complement communication objectives, target audiences, the key messages and images, mediums and means available, and to structure the overall dissemination and communication planning. Overall, this document offers a clear path as guidance to all the foreseen

communication and dissemination activities of DE-RISK. As the project progresses, there will be more opportunities identified and approached. In this regard, this Plan will be updated every 6 months according to the changing needs and dynamics of the project.

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DE-RISK